

The Psychology of Landscapes: An Integrative Framework

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Abstract

Landscapes shape and are shaped by human psychology. This paper introduces the Landscape Features Framework, a two-level framework that operationalizes landscapes as (a) low-level, modality-specific features (e.g., visual, acoustic, olfactory, haptic) and (b) high-level, structural features (e.g., land cover, topography, accessibility, resource availability). The framework presents how landscape types (forests, coastal areas, cultivated land) can be systematically studied as a conglomerate of low- and high-level landscape features that influence and are influenced by psychological outcomes. The paper outlines how the framework relates to existing theories that link psychology to landscapes and conclude by presenting future research avenues that apply our framework.

Keywords: landscapes, geography, emotion, personality, cognition, wellbeing

The Psychology of Landscapes: An Integrative Framework

“I felt my lungs inflate with the onrush of scenery—air, mountains, trees, people. I thought, ‘This is what it is to be happy.’” In her quote, Sylvia Plath expounds on how the experience of being in a landscape, defined by its visual, olfactory, acoustic, and tactile properties, impacts one’s psychological state. To date, the relationship between landscapes and human psychology that Sylvia Plath captures has been repeatedly confirmed. Growing interest in the psychology of landscapes has led researchers to test and find evidence for landscapes’ impact on emotional states (Meidenbauer et al., 2020), cognition (Talhelm et al., 2014), behavior (Aiello et al., 2025), personality (Götz et al., 2020), and mental health (Bratman et al., 2015). The positioning of highways (Aiello et al., 2025), the accessibility to public spaces (Park, 2017), the walkability of the city (Oishi, Saeki, & Axt, 2015), all guide our behavior and impact our everyday lives. Landscapes appear to systematically relate to psychological outcomes. Yet, much of the evidence is scattered across a range of disciplines, from environmental to epidemiological and psychological studies, where landscapes are differently operationalized, measured, and tested. This growing body of evidence has urged the World Health Organization to call for a systematic enquiry into how different types of landscapes impact psychological phenomena (Braubach et al., 2021). It is therefore timely to revisit how landscapes are investigated in relation to psychological outcomes. The current paper seeks to address this call by proposing the Landscape Features Framework—a two-level model that operationalizes landscapes in terms of their low- and high-level features.

First, I outline what the psychology of landscapes is concerned with and why it warrants dedicated investigation. I continue by outlining the core elements of the framework, presenting low- and high-level landscape features as tools for the operationalization of landscapes. Next, I integrate the framework with current theories relevant to the psychology of landscapes. The framework proposes a cumulative, interactionist account of landscapes,

needed to robustly investigate the psychology of landscapes. Last, I elaborate on how the Landscape Features Framework can be employed in future research.

Landscape Features Framework

Despite the growing literature on the psychology of landscapes, evidence remains scattered across disciplines and theoretical strands. While ecological and geographical sciences are largely interested in the high-level, structural associations between granular types of landscapes and human behavior (e.g., Foster et al., 2003; Nagendra et al., 2004, Thompson, 2011), epidemiological sciences tend to be interested in large-scale associations between landscape types and wellbeing (e.g., Sugiyama et al., 2008; Triguero-Mas et al., 2015), and environmental psychology tends to be interested in either low-level or high-level features of landscapes and their association with human emotion (e.g., Bringslimark, Hartig, & Patil, 2009; Hartmann & Apaolaza-Ibañez, 2010; Militaru et al., 2025), cognition (e.g., Raanaas et al., 2011; Sharam, Mayer, & Baumann, 2023), or behavior (Zhang et al., 2023). Despite this divide, there is considerable overlap of paradigms, vocabulary and methodology, which contribute to a converging literature, with notable examples of interdisciplinary output (e.g., Hartig et al., 2014; White et al., 2013; Beyer et al., 2014; Bratman et al., 2019).

The proposed framework aims to collate the existing evidence into a unified model, by serving two important purposes. First, the framework aims to serve as a catalogue that indexes operationalizations of landscapes currently scattered across numerous disciplines. Second, it serves as a canvas for further systematization of the cumulative, interactionist study of landscape features, highlighting new areas of study.

Studying Landscapes as Features

The framework posits that across all the related domains, landscape types can be studied either in terms of the low-level, modality-specific features (colors, smells, sounds, textures) that make up the landscape, or in terms of their high-level, structural features that

capture broad patterns of landscape organization (land cover, resources, topography, accessibility). The two landscape characteristics—low-level and high-level landscape features—define the psychological experience of landscapes (Figure 1; Box 1), yet they are not treated as orthogonal nor hierarchical; instead, they concomitantly contribute to the psychological experience of landscapes.

Figure 1
Landscape Features Framework

Landscape Types

In the Landscape Features Framework, landscape “type” refers to the spatially organized configuration of low- and high-level features. For example, the study of forests—a landscape *type*—can be operationalized as the combination of high canopy density (high-level feature), low decibels level, color properties (low-level features) etc.

Landscape typologies effectively act as labels that systematically organize low-level and high-level features and can reconstructed from feature vectors. Different taxonomies categorize landscapes with varying degrees of granularity. Binary categorizations classify landscapes as either natural or human made. In contrast, other taxonomies differentiate between 10 or more granular landscape categories. While the literature has been

predominantly concentrated on binary categorizations of landscapes, more granular landscape types have started to receive considerable attention (Ward Thompson, 2016). Gardens (De Bell et al., 2020), parks (Każmierczak, 2013), forests (Oh et al., 2017) or seaside (Garrett et al., 2019) have been shown to have distinct relationships with psychological outcomes (Garrett et al., 2023; Maas et al., 2009; White et al., 2021), making such granular taxonomies suitable for the study of the psychology of landscapes. Table 1 presents an outline of how different taxonomies of landscape types map to landscape features.

Low-level Features of Landscapes

Low-level features of landscapes refer to fine-grained attributes that make up landscapes—including visual, olfactory, acoustic or tactile properties. Studies of low-level landscapes' features typically investigate the granular sources of landscapes' salutogenic effect (e.g., “Do colors occurring in forests impact psychological outcomes?”). In contrast to studies of high-level landscape features, studies of low-level landscape features manipulate or isolate singular characteristics of the landscape in question. Low-level features are experienced at small geographical and temporal scale (Box 1).

Extant literature elaborates on what low-level features relate to psychological outcomes. Multi-modal properties of landscapes, such as visual, acoustic, haptic, and olfactory, have been found to impact psychological outcomes. Visual features of landscapes, such as color, contrast, brightness or contour properties have been linked to emotions (O'Dea et al., 2025; Farzanfar & Bernhardt-Walther, 2023) and psychophysiological measures of relaxation (Elsadek & Fujii, 2014). Sounds found in natural landscapes, such as birdsong, wind, and water sounds, have been linked to increases in mood and cognitive performance, and to reductions in arousal levels compared to sounds from built landscapes (Ratcliffe, 2021; Medvedev et al., 2015). Tactile interaction with elements of the natural environment such as wood or flowers was found to increase restoration (Kim, Choi, & Park, 2023). Olfactory

properties of landscapes are also linked to emotion, emotion regulation, cognitive function, social interactions, and stress levels (Bratman et al., 2024; Boesveldt & Parma, 2021).

Unpleasant odours commonly encountered in urban, densely populated areas—such as emissions, waste, or tobacco smoke (Quercia et al., 2015)—can have a direct negative impact on residents’ wellbeing and quality of life (Baker et al., 2018). Such studies showcase how low-level features can be effectively isolated or manipulated to identify the granular characteristics of landscapes that can influence psychological outcomes.

Box 1. *Low- and high-level features defined in terms of scale, manipulability and associated measures.*

<p>Low-level Landscape Features</p>	<p>Visual </p>	<p>Scale: Small geographical and temporal scale (~centimeters, minutes)</p> <p>Manipulability: Directly manipulable (laboratory, field or quasi-experiments)</p> <p>Measures: Visual (hue, brightness, saturation, contour); Acoustic (sound pressure level, event density); Olfactory (odor categories, volatile organic compounds); Haptic (texture, temperature).</p>
<p>High-level Landscape Features</p>	<p>Land cover </p>	<p>Scale: Large geographical and temporal scale (~hundreds of meters, years)</p> <p>Manipulability: Indirectly manipulable (longitudinal designs, natural experiments, cross-sectional designs)</p> <p>Measures: Land surface (land cover composition, normalized difference vegetation index), topography (elevation, viewshed area), accessibility (walkability, population density).</p>

High-Level Features of Landscapes

High-level, distal features of landscapes refer to broad, distal, and structural properties, such as land cover, elevation, resource availability or accessibility. Aggregate or spatially distributed patterns that define landscapes are studied in relation to individual or aggregate-level psychological outcomes, mapped at the associated geographical level (e.g., “Is the amount of built-up land associated with residents’ psychological outcomes?”). In contrast with studies of low-level landscape features, studies of high-level landscape features are concerned with distal characteristics of landscapes which are indirectly measured and are more difficult to manipulate experimentally. High-level features are experienced at large geographical and temporal scale (Box 1).

Extant literature elaborates on what and how high-level features relate to psychological outcomes. Land cover, topography, accessibility, and resource availability are examples of such high-level features. Growing literature on land cover identifies how systematic variation in the material that covers the Earth’s surface is associated with humans’ emotions (MacKerron & Mourato, 2013), cognitions (Lega et al., 2021), personality (Militaru et al., 2024), and wellbeing (Li & Managi, 2021). Similarly, landscapes’ elevation has been shown to meaningfully relate to regional personality. Mountainous areas, defined by their higher elevation, were found to correlate with regional personality (Götz et al., 2020) and be preferred by those more introverted (Oishi et al., 2015). Accessibility, capturing opportunities for interaction (Geurs & Van Wee, 2004), has been related to many measures of public wellbeing. Oishi and colleagues (2015) found that people living in more walkable areas report being healthier than those in less walkable regions. The availability of resources within a landscape has also been shown to shape agricultural practices and subsistence styles, influencing patterns of cognition (e.g., Uskul et al., 2008; Glowacki & Molleman, 2017).

Overall, these studies showcase what and how high-level features relate to psychological outcomes.

Concomitant Study of Low- and High-Level Features

Landscapes can be effectively operationalized either in terms of their low- or high-level features. However, experientially, low- and high-level features can be perceived in tandem: We may perceive colors at the same time as we experience the undulation of faraway hills. Low-level and high-level features can also be mutually defined. We can define landscapes' elevation (high-level feature) by its visual outline (low-level feature). Similarly, we can define land cover (high-level feature) by its unique combination of colors, textures, sounds and smells (low-level features). This concomitant manifestation of low- and high-level landscape features has already been integrated methodologically and studied across related fields of research. For instance, acoustic biodiversity (low-level) has been found to enhance perceived wilderness (high-level) and, in turn, amplify the restorative effects of natural landscapes (e.g., Fisher et al., 2021). Scenes that encompass high proportions of water bodies and vegetation (high-level) have fractal properties (low-level) that people tend to prefer (Hagerhall et al., 2004; Taylor et al., 2011). The concomitant operationalization of landscapes through their low- and high-level features allows researchers to systematically generate and test hypotheses (e.g., if land cover is robustly associated with wellbeing measures, how much of this effect can be causally attributed to color preferences?). More importantly, a simultaneous investigation of low- and high-level features addresses important questions about the interaction, causality, scale, and the function of landscapes in human psychology. As an illustration, Table 2 presents and summarizes extant research on the psychology of landscapes as a function of landscape features and landscape types across psychological domains.

The operationalization of landscapes as low- and high-level features paves the way to studying interactive effects. It is plausible that the construal of high-level features (e.g., high canopy density) is moderated by low-level features: A forest characterized by a dense canopy in bright settings can be relaxing and calming, but unnerving in darkness. Such interaction between low- and high-level features matches subjective experience of landscapes, when both features are experienced concomitantly. Several studies found supporting evidence for an interaction between low- and high-level features. One recent study found that greenery is a protective factor against minimal noise annoyance, but not protective against high noise levels (Pasanen et al., 2025). In another study congruency between audio and visual features was found to influence landscape preference: Adding natural sounds to natural visual landscapes is preferred over adding urban sounds to natural visual landscapes (Carle, Barrio, & De Lucio, 1999). Concomitantly operationalizing landscapes in terms of both low- and high-level features systematizes the study of interactive effects that likely capture the lived experience of landscapes.

Psychology Shapes Landscapes

The psychology of landscapes would be incomplete without the acknowledgement of a bilateral relationship between psychology and landscapes. Our emotions, behaviors, cognitions, personality, and wellbeing can fundamentally shape landscapes and drive concrete landscape conservation efforts. For example, emotions, such as hope (Geiger, Dwyer, & Swim, 2023), nostalgia (De Vroey, 2023) or anger (Contreras et al., 2024) contribute towards conservation efforts such as rewilding or biodiversity preservation in natural landscapes (Brosch & Sauter, 2023; Brick, Nielsen, & Hofmann, 2023). Visiting natural landscapes at least once a week and feeling connected to nature increased behaviors such as recycling, buying sustainable products, or choosing sustainable transportation (Martin et al., 2020). A meta-analysis further confirmed that feeling more connected to nature makes individuals

more likely to act pro-environmentally (Mackay et al., 2019). Additionally, positive affect can act as motivator for pro-environmental choices (Shiota et al., 2021). Cognitions, such as risk perception (Tam & McDaniels, 2013) or confirmation bias (Nickerson, 2003) can also contribute towards attitudes towards landscape conservation initiatives: Individuals who perceive environmental risks as personally relevant are more likely to engage in conservation behaviors (Saari et al., 2021). Personality traits such as agreeableness, openness to experience and conscientiousness are associated with greater environmental concern and pro-environmental behaviors at both individual and country-level (Milfond & Sibley, 2012). In turn, at aggregate, regional level, residents' spending behaviors and personality can be reflected in changes in the local amenities landscape (Ebert et al., 2021); sustainable choices can thus cumulatively and interactively shape changes in human-built landscapes. It is evident that our thoughts, feelings, behaviors or attitudes towards high-level, structural elements of landscapes can influence subsequent interactions with the said environment. Similarly, it is plausible that psychological attitudes towards low-level features of landscapes can influence subsequent behaviors.

The Landscape Features Framework advances the study of cumulative and interactive contribution of landscape features by systematizing the object of study and by providing a unified set of methodological operationalizations. In practice, the framework can be used to identify research gaps in the study how low- and high-level features of landscapes interact to influence psychological outcomes. The Landscape Features Framework specifies *what* to measure and *at what scale* (low- and high-level features), supplying measurable variables that can test pathways from landscapes to psychological states, traits, and behaviors.

Table 1. *Illustration of systematization of extant research through the Landscape Features Framework.*

Feature Level (Low/High)	Feature Variable(s)	Landscape Type	Psychological Variable(s)	Method	Reference	Summary
Low-level Visual	Depth of view	Natural/Urban landscapes	Emotion: positive affect	Field experiment	Olszewska-Guizzo et al., 2022	Long-distance view in a landscape scene was associated with increased positive affect and neurological measures of mindfulness and relaxation.
Low-level Acoustic	Natural versus urban soundscapes	Natural/Urban landscapes	Cognition; Emotion: directed attention; positive and negative affect	Laboratory experiment	Van Hedger et al., 2018	Cognitive performance was improved among participants exposed to sounds found in natural versus urban landscapes.
Low-level Olfactory	Smellscapes	Urban landscape	Emotion: happiness, familiarity, relaxation, calming etc.	Field study/Smell maps	Xiao, Tait, & Kang, 2020	Smellscapes evoke distinct emotions in urban landscapes through nine identified perceptual patterns.
Low-level Haptic	Solar radiation, temperature, wind speed, humidity	Urban green area, urban built-up area	Psychophysiology: skin conductance, skin temperature, heart rate variability, thermal comfort	Field experiment	Liu et al., 2019	Psychophysiological measures indicative of stress levels decreased when participants were exposed to an urban green area compared to an urban built-up area.

<p>High-level</p> <p>Land cover</p>	<p>Land cover categories: cultivated land, forest, grassland, shrub, wetland, water bodies, tundra, artificial surface, bare land, glaciers and permanent snow, ocean.</p>	<p>Landscape types: 11 land cover categories</p>	<p>Personality: Big Five traits</p>	<p>Correlational</p>	<p>Militaru et al., 2024</p>	<p>Robust associations were found between regional personality traits and land cover types where human intervention was present such as coastal, urban, and cultivated areas.</p>
<p>High-level</p> <p>Topography</p>	<p>Elevation</p>	<p>Mountains</p>	<p>Personality: Big Five traits</p>	<p>Correlational</p>	<p>Götz et al., 2020</p>	<p>Mountainous areas were found to be higher on openness to experience and lower on agreeableness, extraversion, neuroticism, and conscientiousness.</p>
<p>High-level</p> <p>Accessibility</p>	<p>Walkability index</p>	<p>Urban highways, main avenues, local streets</p>	<p>Wellbeing: Subjective wellbeing indicators</p>	<p>Correlational</p>	<p>Lucchesi et al., 2021</p>	<p>Walkability, defined as sidewalk condition, comfort, attractiveness, and traffic safety as self-reported by participants, was positively associated with residents' subjective wellbeing.</p>
<p>High-level:</p> <p>Resources</p>	<p>Subsistence practice (rice vs wheat)</p>	<p>Agricultural landscapes</p>	<p>Cognition: holistic vs analytic thinking</p>	<p>Quasi-experiment</p>	<p>Talhelm et al., 2014</p>	<p>Rice-growing regions in China were more holistic thinking than wheat-growing regions.</p>

Mechanisms Underlying the Psychology to Landscapes

The Landscape Features Framework aims to offer a methodological map, useful in answering theoretically relevant questions through systematic operationalization of core concepts. As such, this framework can be usefully employed to systematize theoretical strands relevant to the psychology of landscapes but does not intend to replace them. Instead, it advances that extant theories act as mechanisms in the study of the psychology of landscapes. In the following section, I elaborate on how the Landscape Features Framework sits within five extant mechanistic theories of the psychology of landscapes.

Psycho-Evolutionary Theory

Urban landscapes require immediate action and sustained attention either to cross the street, take the right turn, or avoid pedestrians and cars. Natural landscapes, on the other hand, do not require such immediate action as they allow for a ‘soft involvement of cognition’ (Ulrich, 1983) which in turn leads to positive emotional states. The psycho-evolutionary theory put forward by Ulrich and colleagues formalized this intuition and posited that contact with nature allows for psychophysiological stress recovery through the attributes of the natural environment such as spatial openness, the presence of diverse patterns, or water features (Ulrich, 1983; Ulrich et al., 1991). In turn, attending to these features rapidly elicits positive affect and blocks negative affect by decreasing physiological activation. Empirical studies bring support for this intuition. Studies exploring the psycho-evolutionary theory are typically concerned with the direct exposure to natural environment, thus broadly studying high-level landscape features where landscape types are either understood in a binary manner (nature vs human-made) or more granularly. For example, one study investigated and found that short 15-minute walks in a nature preserve with woods and creeks led to significant increases in positive affect compared to walks in urban landscapes (Mayer et al., 2008).

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More recent investigations related to landscapes' restorative effects concomitantly study low- and high-level features of landscapes. For example, O'Dea and colleagues (2025) measured boredom, awe, sadness, and happiness before and after exposure to images of natural and artificial landscape types (high-level features). Compared to baseline measures, natural landscapes increased happiness and awe, while reducing sadness and boredom, an effect partly attributed to the vividness of colors found in nature (low-level features).

Attention Restoration Theory

One notable theoretical contribution linking landscapes to cognition is the attention restoration theory advanced by Kaplan and Kaplan (1989): Natural landscapes restore attention by offering 'soft fascinations'—stimuli that gently capture attention without requiring effortful engagement (Home et al., 2012; Kaplan & Kaplan, 1989). Empirical studies provide support: Nature inspires appreciation for its beautiful scenery and, in turn, leads to increased aesthetic valuations (Anderson et al., 2018; Farzanfar & Walther, 2023).

Typical investigations of the attention restoration theory involve measures of high-level landscape features, via direct or virtual exposure to types of landscapes of varying granularity (Ohly et al., 2016). For instance, one study using a randomized crossover trial investigated whether walking in an urban versus natural landscape increases performance during a backward digit span task (Berman, 2008). In the attention restoration literature, cross-over investigations between low- and high-level landscape features exist. One such example is the study by Evensen and colleagues (2015) where they measured the restoration effects of seeing live plants, inanimate objects of a control (low-level features), all with or without a window view (high-level feature).

Affordances Theory

Landscapes provide the broader canvas of our daily lives, guiding leisure activities, walking or driving routes (Götz, Yoshino et al., 2020), socialization opportunities (Doughty,

2013), and, importantly, dictating resource and food availability (Uskul et al., 2008; Talhelm et al., 2014). This line of reasoning is captured by the theory of affordances put forward by Gibson in 1979. Affordances, in Gibson's framework, are understood as 'what [the environment] offers the animal, what it provides or furnishes'. Landscapes can be understood as affordances insofar as they provide and shape the spaces suitable for a range of activities. For instance, parks can offer opportunities for people to engage in physical activities: People are more likely to jog or walk recreationally if there are nearby parks or trails that appear attractive (Zhang et al., 2019; Meagher, 2020).

The layout of cities can also significantly impact and shape people's opportunities for social interactions. Green landscapes, such as parks or gardens, often act as 'third places' where people gather for the purposes of human connection, outside of work or home settings (Oldenburg & Brissett, 1982; Oldenburg, 1989). The quantity and quality of streetscape greenery is associated with decreased crime rates (Kuo & Sullivan, 2001) and better perceived social cohesion (De Vries et al., 2013; Sugiyama et al., 2008).

Important features of landscapes can, however, moderate the relationship between high-level landscape features and psychological outcomes. Arguably, urban greenery must provide recreational features and be well maintained to encourage socialization behaviors (Kazmierczak, 2013). Although urban greenery is generally associated with feelings of safety, green spaces enclosed in highly dense urban areas can decrease such feelings (Maas et al., 2009). The Landscape Features Framework can provide a toolkit for further studies into how low- and high-level features interact to impact safety perceptions and wellbeing levels by asking whether low-level features (e.g., depth of view, fractal properties) interact with high-level features (e.g., built-up or green areas density) by dampening or heightening perceptions of safety. Such interactive study designs should be used to identify the specific features of landscapes that can be modified to positively impact psychological outcomes.

Subsistence Styles Theory

Subsistence styles theory posits that existing ecological affordances narrow the choices for agricultural practices (Uskul et al., 2008). For instance, paddy rice requires large amounts of water, which makes rice-growing more viable in water-abundant regions. In turn, rice-growing requires group collaboration, whereas wheat is easier to grow and can rely on independent work. Such cooperative or individualistic agricultural practices are associated with regional differences in psychological outcomes: Rice-growing regions are more interdependent and holistic thinking than wheat-growing regions (Talhelm et al., 2014). Such geographical investigations are naturally concerned with high-level operationalizations of landscape features. The subsistence styles theory can be further elaborated by testing the contribution of low-level landscape features, such as landscapes' visual properties. One related example are the studies undertaken by Miyamoto and colleagues (2006) who showed that being exposed to Japanese landscape (high-level features) characterized by more complex and ambiguous objects (low-level features) increased attention to contextual information compared to American landscapes.

Geographical Psychology

Geographical psychology is a model concentrated on the mechanisms behind the spatial organization of psychological phenomena (Rentfrow, 2008; 2020). Rentfrow and colleagues (2008) proposed three mechanisms that give rise to regional differences in psychological outcomes: environmental influence, sociocultural adaptation, and selective migration. The increasing availability of large datasets, spanning across geographies, has enabled researchers to map an array of psychological phenomena and test their association with high-level features of landscapes. Researchers were able to test whether topography, a high-level feature pertaining to the arrangement of a landscape, and land cover are meaningfully related to regional personality (Götz et al., 2020; Xu et al., 2023). Using a large

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personality dataset ($N = 2,690,878$), one study investigated the associations between regional personality and land cover proportions. Land cover types that sustain humans' activities, such as cultivated land and artificial, human-built areas, were found to be associated with regional personality traits (Militaru et al., 2024).

While geographical psychology is largely concerned with the study of high-level features of the environment, such as land cover (Militaru et al., 2024), climate (Wei et al., 2017) or patterns of migration (Jokela, 2009), the Landscape Features Framework advances further questions related to the impact of low-level features on psychological outcomes. One related study investigated how low-level features of participants' rooms such odor, noise levels, temperature or colorfulness were associated with personality traits (Gosling et al., 2002). Such approaches can be usefully extended to studies of low-level landscape features: Are specific low-level features of landscapes preferred by individuals with certain personality traits and does a better feature-personality fit in turn predict improved wellbeing (Götz et al., 2018)?

Further Research

The Landscape Features Framework serves as a unifying methodological bridge for mechanistic theories concerned with the psychology of landscapes, adding to it a common, systematic understanding of the object of study. Building on the low- and high-level features operationalization, many opportunities for fruitful future research become evident. Three such avenues are highlighted below.

First, scholars can ensure the concomitant study of low- and high-level features to test causal links. While a concomitant, interactionist approach is not novel, extant scholarly investigations have concentrated on either constituent or structural characteristics of landscapes, with some notable examples of concomitant study emerging (Hagerhall et al., 2004; Taylor et al., 2011; O'Dea et al., 2025). The concomitant operationalization of

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landscapes as features answers important questions: (1) Are high-level, structural elements of landscapes influencing psychology in isolation of low-level features? (2) Are low-level, constituent elements of landscapes influencing psychology in isolation of high-level features? (3) How much do low- and high-level features of landscapes contribute towards psychological outcomes? (4) How do low- and high-level features interact to influence psychological outcomes?

Second, a notable question concerns how the changing landscapes impact psychological outcomes. Damaged habitats, either through deforestation or urbanization, degrade biodiversity and actively reconfigure land cover composition (De Lange et al., 2022). These alterations occur at both levels: There are changes to low-level features (e.g., reduced acoustic biodiversity, altered visual properties) and high-level features (e.g., land cover modification, accessibility). These modifications plausibly affect thoughts, feelings, and behaviors, yet their impact and mechanisms remain understudied.

Conclusion

Understanding the connection between psychology and landscapes seems particularly timely given that some of the most pressing issues of humankind—climate change, loss of biodiversity, loss of natural habitats—rest upon our common understanding of how humans interact with the spaces in which they reside.

Studying landscapes as low or high-level features provides an organized way to methodologically approach the study of the psychology of landscapes. In so doing, we hope to provide a conceptual bridge between otherwise disjoint literatures, all preoccupied with the study of landscapes.

References

- Aiello, L. M., Vybornova, A., Juhász, S., Szell, M., & Bokányi, E. (2025). Urban highways are barriers to social ties. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, *122*(10), e2408937122. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2408937122>
- Anderson, C. L., Monroy, M., & Keltner, D. (2018). Awe in nature heals: Evidence from military veterans, at-risk youth, and college students. *Emotion*, *18*(8), 1195. <https://doi.org/10.1037/emo0000442>
- Baker, K. L., Dickinson, M., Findley, T. M., Gire, D. H., Louis, M., Suver, M. P., ... & Smear, M. C. (2018). Algorithms for olfactory search across species. *Journal of Neuroscience*, *38*(44), 9383–9389. <https://doi.org/10.1523/jneurosci.1668-18.2018>
- Berman, M. G., Jonides, J., & Kaplan, S. (2008). The cognitive benefits of interacting with nature. *Psychological Science*, *19*(12), 1207–1212. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9280.2008.02225.x>
- Beyer, K. M., Kaltenbach, A., Szabo, A., Bogar, S., Nieto, F. J., & Malecki, K. M. (2014). Exposure to neighborhood green space and mental health: Evidence from the Survey of the Health of Wisconsin. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, *11*(3), 3453–3472. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph110303453>
- Boesveldt, S., & Parma, V. (2021). The importance of the olfactory system in human well-being, through nutrition and social behavior. *Cell and Tissue Research*, *383*(1), 559–567. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00441-020-03367-7>
- Bratman, G. N., Anderson, C. B., Berman, M. G., Cochran, B., De Vries, S., Flanders, J., ... & Daily, G. C. (2019). Nature and mental health: An ecosystem service perspective. *Science Advances*, *5*(7), eaax0903. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.aax0903>

PSYCHOLOGY OF LANDSCAPES

- Bratman, G. N., Bembibre, C., Daily, G. C., Doty, R. L., Hummel, T., Jacobs, L. F., ... & Spengler, J. D. (2024). Nature and human well-being: The olfactory pathway. *Science Advances*, *10*(20), eadn3028. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.adn3028>
- Bratman, G. N., Hamilton, J. P., Hahn, K. S., Daily, G. C., & Gross, J. J. (2015). Nature experience reduces rumination and subgenual prefrontal cortex activation. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, *112*(28), 8567–8572. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1510459112>
- Braubach, M., Kendrovski, V., Jarosinska, D., Mudu, P., Andreucci, M. B., Beute, F., Davies, Z., de Vries, S., Glanville, J., & Keune, H. (2021). *Green and blue spaces and mental health: New evidence and perspectives for action*. <https://repository.uantwerpen.be/docman/irua/19cce3/179537.pdf>
- Brick, C., Nielsen, K. S., & Hofmann, W. (2023). Opportunities for emotion research on biodiversity. *Emotion Review*, *15*(4), 263–266. <https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/9pt5v>
- Bringslimark, T., Hartig, T., & Patil, G. G. (2009). The psychological benefits of indoor plants: A critical review of the experimental literature. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, *29*(4), 422–433. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2009.05.001>
- Brosch, T., & Sauter, D. (2023). Emotions and the climate crisis: A research agenda for an affective sustainability science. *Emotion Review*, *15*(4), 253–257. <https://doi.org/10.1177/17540739231193741>
- Capaldi, C. A., Passmore, H. A., Nisbet, E. K., Zelenski, J. M., & Dopko, R. L. (2015). Flourishing in nature: A review of the benefits of connecting with nature and its application as a wellbeing intervention. *International Journal of Wellbeing*, *5*(4). <https://doi.org/10.5502/ijw.v5i4.449>
- Contreras, A., Blanchard, M. A., Mougouama-Daouda, C., & Heeren, A. (2024). When eco-anger (but not eco-anxiety nor eco-sadness) makes you change! A temporal network

PSYCHOLOGY OF LANDSCAPES

approach to the emotional experience of climate change. *Journal of Anxiety Disorders*, 102, 102822. <https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/sp8hn>

De Bell, S., White, M., Griffiths, A., Darlow, A., Taylor, T., Wheeler, B., & Lovell, R. (2020). Spending time in the garden is positively associated with health and wellbeing: Results from a national survey in England. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 200, 103836. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2020.103836>

De Lange, E., Sharkey, W., Castelló y Tickell, S., Migné, J., Underhill, R., & Milner-Gulland, E. J. (2022). Communicating the biodiversity crisis: From “warnings” to positive engagement. *Tropical Conservation Science*, 15, 19400829221134893. <https://doi.org/10.1177/19400829221134893>

De Vries, S., Van Dillen, S. M., Groenewegen, P. P., & Spreeuwenberg, P. (2013). Streetscape greenery and health: Stress, social cohesion and physical activity as mediators. *Social Science & Medicine*, 94, 26–33. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2013.06.030>

De Vroey, L. (2023). Back to the future: Retrospectivity, recovery, and nostalgia in rewilding. *Environmental Ethics*, 45(4), 359–380. <https://doi.org/10.5840/enviroethics202383167>

Doughty, K. (2013). Walking together: The embodied and mobile production of a therapeutic landscape. *Health & Place*, 24, 140–146. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.healthplace.2013.08.009>

Ebert, T., Götz, F. M., Gladstone, J. J., Müller, S. R., & Matz, S. C. (2021). Spending reflects not only who we are but also who we are around: The joint effects of individual and geographic personality on consumption. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 121(2), 378. <https://doi.org/10.1037/pspp0000344>

PSYCHOLOGY OF LANDSCAPES

- Elsadek, M., & Fujii, E. (2014). People's psycho-physiological responses to plantscape colors stimuli: A pilot study. *International Journal of Psychology and Behavioral Sciences*, 4, 70–78.
- Evensen, K. H., Raanaas, R. K., Hagerhall, C. M., Johansson, M., & Patil, G. G. (2015). Restorative elements at the computer workstation: A comparison of live plants and inanimate objects with and without window view. *Environment and Behavior*, 47(3), 288–303. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013916513499584>
- Farzanfar, D., & Walther, D. B. (2023). Changing what you like: Modifying contour properties shifts aesthetic valuations of scenes. *Psychological Science*, 34(10), 1101–1120. <https://doi.org/10.1177/09567976231190546>
- Fisher, J. C., Irvine, K. N., Bicknell, J. E., Hayes, W. M., Fernandes, D., Mistry, J., & Davies, Z. G. (2021). Perceived biodiversity, sound, naturalness and safety enhance the restorative quality and wellbeing benefits of green and blue space in a neotropical city. *Science of the Total Environment*, 755, 143095. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.143095>
- Foley, L., Prins, R., Crawford, F., Humphreys, D., Mitchell, R., Sahlqvist, S., Thomson, H., Ogilvie, D., & M74 Study Team. (2017). Effects of living near an urban motorway on the wellbeing of local residents in deprived areas: Natural experimental study. *PLOS ONE*, 12(4), e0174882. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0174882>
- Fong, K. C., Hart, J. E., & James, P. (2018). A review of epidemiologic studies on greenness and health: Updated literature through 2017. *Current Environmental Health Reports*, 5, 77–87. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40572-018-0179-y>
- Foster, D., Swanson, F., Aber, J., Burke, I., Brokaw, N., Tilman, D., & Knapp, A. (2003). The importance of land-use legacies to ecology and conservation. *BioScience*, 53(1), 77–88. [https://doi.org/10.1641/0006-3568\(2003\)053\[0077:tiolul\]2.0.co;2](https://doi.org/10.1641/0006-3568(2003)053[0077:tiolul]2.0.co;2)

PSYCHOLOGY OF LANDSCAPES

- Frumkin, H., Bratman, G. N., Breslow, S. J., Cochran, B., Kahn, P. H., Jr., Lawler, J. J., ... & Wood, S. A. (2017). Nature contact and human health: A research agenda. *Environmental Health Perspectives*, *125*(7), 075001. <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp1663>
- Garrett, J. K., Clitherow, T. J., White, M. P., Wheeler, B. W., & Fleming, L. E. (2019). Coastal proximity and mental health among urban adults in England: The moderating effect of household income. *Health & Place*, *59*, 102200. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.healthplace.2019.102200>
- Garrett, J. K., Rowney, F. M., White, M. P., Lovell, R., Fry, R. J., Akbari, A., ... & Wheeler, B. W. (2023). Visiting nature is associated with lower socioeconomic inequalities in well-being in Wales. *Scientific Reports*, *13*(1), 9684. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-35427-7>
- Geiger, N., Dwyer, T., & Swim, J. K. (2023). Hopium or empowering hope? A meta-analysis of hope and climate engagement. *Frontiers in Psychology*, *14*, 1139427. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1139427>
- Geurs, K. T., & Van Wee, B. (2004). Accessibility evaluation of land-use and transport strategies: Review and research directions. *Journal of Transport Geography*, *12*(2), 127–140. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2003.10.005>
- Glowacki, L., & Molleman, L. (2017). Subsistence styles shape human social learning strategies. *Nature Human Behaviour*, *1*(5), 0098. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-017-0098>
- Gosling, S. D., Ko, S. J., Mannarelli, T., & Morris, M. E. (2002). A room with a cue: Personality judgments based on offices and bedrooms. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, *82*(3), 379. <https://doi.org/10.1037//0022-3514.82.3.379>

PSYCHOLOGY OF LANDSCAPES

- Götz, F. M., Stieger, S., Gosling, S. D., Potter, J., & Rentfrow, P. J. (2020). Physical topography is associated with human personality. *Nature Human Behaviour*, 4(11), 1135–1144. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-020-0930-x>
- Götz, F. M., Yoshino, S., & Oshio, A. (2020). The association between walkability and personality: Evidence from a large socioecological study in Japan. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 69, 101438. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2020.101438>
- Gould, P. (1996). Space, time and the human being. *International Social Science Journal*, 48(150), 449–460. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2451.1996.tb00099.x>
- Hagerhall, C. M., Purcell, T., & Taylor, R. (2004). Fractal dimension of landscape silhouette outlines as a predictor of landscape preference. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 24(2), 247–255. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2003.12.004>
- Hartig, T., Mitchell, R., De Vries, S., & Frumkin, H. (2014). Nature and health. *Annual Review of Public Health*, 35, 207–228. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-publhealth-032013-182443>
- Hartmann, P., & Apaolaza-Ibáñez, V. (2010). Beyond savanna: An evolutionary and environmental psychology approach to behavioral effects of nature scenery in green advertising. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 30(1), 119–128. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2009.10.001>
- Home, R., Hunziker, M., & Bauer, N. (2012). Psychosocial outcomes as motivations for visiting nearby urban green spaces. *Leisure Sciences*, 34(4), 350–365. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01490400.2012.687644>
- Jokela, M. (2009). Personality predicts migration within and between US states. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 43(1), 79–83. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrp.2008.09.005>
- Kaplan, R., & Kaplan, S. (1989). *The experience of nature: A psychological perspective*. Cambridge University Press.

PSYCHOLOGY OF LANDSCAPES

- Kaźmierczak, A. (2013). The contribution of local parks to neighbourhood social ties. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, *109*(1), 31–44.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2012.05.007>
- Kim, Y. J., Choi, S. W., & Park, S. A. (2023). Effects of tactile stimulation using an assortment of natural elements on the psychophysiological responses of adults. *Horticulturae*, *9*(12), 1293. <https://doi.org/10.3390/horticulturae9121293>
- Kitayama, S., Ishii, K., Imada, T., Takemura, K., & Ramaswamy, J. (2006). Voluntary settlement and the spirit of independence: Evidence from Japan's northern frontier. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, *91*(3), 369–384. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.91.3.369>
- Kuo, F. E., & Sullivan, W. C. (2001). Environment and crime in the inner city: Does vegetation reduce crime? *Environment and Behavior*, *33*(3), 343–367.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/00139160121973025>
- Lega, C., Gidlow, C., Jones, M., Ellis, N., & Hurst, G. (2021). The relationship between surrounding greenness, stress and memory. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening*, *59*, 126974. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2020.126974>
- Li, C., & Managi, S. (2021). Land cover matters to human well-being. *Scientific Reports*, *11*(1), 15957. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-95351-6>
- Liu, B., Lian, Z., & Brown, R. D. (2019). Effect of landscape microclimates on thermal comfort and physiological wellbeing. *Sustainability*, *11*(19), 5387.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/su11195387>
- Lucchesi, S. T., Larranaga, A. M., Ochoa, J. A. A., Samios, A. A. B., & Cybis, H. B. B. (2021). The role of security and walkability in subjective wellbeing: A multigroup analysis among different age cohorts. *Research in Transportation Business & Management*, *40*, 100559. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rtbm.2020.100559>

- Maas, J., Spreeuwenberg, P., van Winsum-Westra, M., Verheij, R. A., Vries, S., & Groenewegen, P. P. (2009). Is green space in the living environment associated with people's feelings of social safety? *Environment and Planning A*, *41*(7), 1763–1777. <https://doi.org/10.1068/a4196>
- Mackay, C. M., & Schmitt, M. T. (2019). Do people who feel connected to nature do more to protect it? A meta-analysis. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, *65*, 101323. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2019.101323>
- MacKerron, G., & Mourato, S. (2013). Happiness is greater in natural environments. *Global Environmental Change*, *23*(5), 992–1000. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2013.03.010>
- Martin, L., White, M. P., Hunt, A., Richardson, M., Pahl, S., & Burt, J. (2020). Nature contact, nature connectedness and associations with health, wellbeing and pro-environmental behaviors. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, *68*, 101389. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2020.101389>
- Mayer, F. S., Frantz, C. M., Bruehlman-Senecal, E., & Dolliver, K. (2009). Why is nature beneficial? The role of connectedness to nature. *Environment and Behavior*, *41*(5), 607–643. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013916508319745>
- Meagher, B. R. (2020). Ecologizing social psychology: The physical environment as a necessary constituent of social processes. *Personality and Social Psychology Review*, *24*(1), 3–23. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1088868319845938>
- Medvedev, O., Shepherd, D., & Hautus, M. J. (2015). The restorative potential of soundscapes: A physiological investigation. *Applied Acoustics*, *96*, 20–26. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apacoust.2015.03.004>
- Meidenbauer, K. L., Stenfors, C. U., Bratman, G. N., Gross, J. J., Schertz, K. E., Choe, K. W., & Berman, M. G. (2020). The affective benefits of nature exposure: What's nature got

to do with it? *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 72, 101498.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2020.101498>

Menatti, L., & Casado da Rocha, A. (2016). Landscape and health: Connecting psychology, aesthetics, and philosophy through the concept of affordance. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 7, 571. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2016.00571>

Milfont, T. L., & Sibley, C. G. (2012). The Big Five personality traits and environmental engagement: Associations at the individual and societal level. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 32(2), 187–195.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2011.12.006>

Militaru, I. E., Serapio-García, G., Ebert, T., Kong, W., Gosling, S. D., Potter, J., Rentfrow, P. J., & Götz, F. M. (2024). The lay of the land: Associations between environmental features and personality. *Journal of Personality*, 00, 1–

23. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jopy.12822>

Militaru, I. E., Van Tilburg, W. A. P., Sedikides, C., Wildschut, T., & Rentfrow, P. J. (2025). Searching for Ithaca: The geography and psychological benefits of nostalgic places. *Current Research in Ecological and Social Psychology*.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cresp.2025.100223>

Miyamoto, Y., Nisbett, R. E., & Masuda, T. (2006). Culture and the physical environment: Holistic versus analytic perceptual affordances. *Psychological Science*, 17(2), 113–119. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9280.2006.01673.x>

Nagendra, H., Munroe, D. K., & Southworth, J. (2004). From pattern to process: Landscape fragmentation and the analysis of land use/land cover change. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 101(2–3), 111–115.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2003.09.003>

PSYCHOLOGY OF LANDSCAPES

- O'Dea, M. K., Militaru, I. E., Igou, E. R., Rentfrow, P. J., Barrett, I., & Van Tilburg, W. A. P. (2025). Nature adds color to life: Less boredom in natural versus artificial environments. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General*.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/xge0001764>
- Oh, B., Lee, K. J., Zaslowski, C., Yeung, A., Rosenthal, D., Larkey, L., & Back, M. (2017). Health and well-being benefits of spending time in forests: Systematic review. *Environmental Health and Preventive Medicine*, 22, 1–11.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12199-017-0677-9>
- Ohly, H., White, M. P., Wheeler, B. W., Bethel, A., Ukoumunne, O. C., Nikolaou, V., & Garside, R. (2016). Attention Restoration Theory: A systematic review of the attention restoration potential of exposure to natural environments. *Journal of Toxicology and Environmental Health, Part B*, 19(7), 305–343.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10937404.2016.1196155>
- Oishi, S., Saeki, M., & Axt, J. (2015). Are people living in walkable areas healthier and more satisfied with life? *Applied Psychology: Health and Well-Being*, 7(3), 365–386.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/aphw.12058>
- Oldenburg, R. (1989). *The great good place*. Marlowe & Company.
- Oldenburg, R., & Brissett, D. (1982). The third place. *Qualitative Sociology*, 5(4), 265–284.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/bf00986754>
- Olszewska-Guizzo, A., Sia, A., Fogel, A., & Ho, R. (2022). Features of urban green spaces associated with positive emotions, mindfulness and relaxation. *Scientific Reports*, 12(1), 20695. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-24637-0>
- Park, K. (2017). Psychological park accessibility: A systematic literature review of perceptual components affecting park use. *Landscape Research*, 42(5), 508–520.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/01426397.2016.1267127>

- Quercia, D., Schifanella, R., Aiello, L. M., & McLean, K. (2015). Smelly maps: The digital life of urban smellscapes. In *Proceedings of the International AAAI Conference on Web and Social Media*, 9(1), 327–336. <https://doi.org/10.1609/icwsm.v9i1.14621>
- Raanaas, R. K., Evensen, K. H., Rich, D., Sjøstrøm, G., & Patil, G. (2011). Benefits of indoor plants on attention capacity in an office setting. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 31(1), 99–105. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2010.11.005>
- Ratcliffe, E. (2021). Sound and soundscape in restorative natural environments: A narrative literature review. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 570563. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.570563>
- Rentfrow, P. J., Gosling, S. D., & Potter, J. (2008). A theory of the emergence, persistence, and expression of geographic variation in psychological characteristics. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 3(5), 339–369. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1745-6924.2008.00084.x>
- Saari, U. A., Damberg, S., Frömbling, L., & Ringle, C. M. (2021). Sustainable consumption behavior of Europeans: The influence of environmental knowledge and risk perception on environmental concern and behavioral intention. *Ecological Economics*, 189, 107155. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2021.107155>
- Sharam, L. A., Mayer, K. M., & Baumann, O. (2023). Design by nature: The influence of windows on cognitive performance and affect. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 85, 101923. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cobeha.2021.04.022>
- Shiota, M. N., Papies, E. K., Preston, S. D., & Sauter, D. A. (2021). Positive affect and behavior change. *Current Opinion in Behavioral Sciences*, 39, 222–228.
- Sugiyama, T., Leslie, E., Giles-Corti, B., & Owen, N. (2008). Associations of neighbourhood greenness with physical and mental health: Do walking, social coherence and local

- social interaction explain the relationships? *Journal of Epidemiology & Community Health*, 62(5), e9. <https://doi.org/10.1136/jech.2007.064287>
- Tam, J., & McDaniels, T. L. (2013). Understanding individual risk perceptions and preferences for climate change adaptations in biological conservation. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 27, 114–123. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2012.12.004>
- Taylor, R. P., Spehar, B., Van Donkelaar, P., & Hagerhall, C. M. (2011). Perceptual and physiological responses to Jackson Pollock's fractals. *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience*, 5, 60.
- Thompson, C. W. (2011). Linking landscape and health: The recurring theme. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 99(3–4), 187–195. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2010.10.006>
- Triguero-Mas, M., Dadvand, P., Cirach, M., Martínez, D., Medina, A., Mompert, A., ... & Nieuwenhuijsen, M. J. (2015). Natural outdoor environments and mental and physical health: Relationships and mechanisms. *Environment International*, 77, 35–41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2015.01.012>
- Ulrich, R. S. (1983). Aesthetic and affective response to natural environment. In *Behavior and the natural environment* (pp. 85–125). Springer US. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4613-3539-9_4
- Ulrich, R. S., Simons, R. F., Losito, B. D., Fiorito, E., Miles, M. A., & Zelson, M. (1991). Stress recovery during exposure to natural and urban environments. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 11(3), 201–230. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0272-4944\(05\)80184-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0272-4944(05)80184-7)
- Uskul, A. K., Kitayama, S., & Nisbett, R. E. (2008). Ecocultural basis of cognition: Farmers and fishermen are more holistic than herders. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 105(25), 8552–8556. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0803874105>

PSYCHOLOGY OF LANDSCAPES

- Van Hedger, S. C., Nusbaum, H. C., Clohisy, L., Jaeggi, S. M., Buschkuhl, M., & Berman, M. G. (2019). Of cricket chirps and car horns: The effect of nature sounds on cognitive performance. *Psychonomic Bulletin & Review*, *26*(2), 522–530. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13423-018-1539-1>
- Ward Thompson, C. (2016). Landscape and Health special issue. *Landscape Research*, *41*(6), 591–597. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01426397.2016.1196878>
- Wei, W., Lu, J. G., Galinsky, A. D., Wu, H., Gosling, S. D., Rentfrow, P. J., ... & Wang, L. (2017). Regional ambient temperature is associated with human personality. *Nature Human Behaviour*, *1*(12), 890–895. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-017-0240-0>
- White, M. P., Alcock, I., Wheeler, B. W., & Depledge, M. H. (2013). Coastal proximity, health and well-being: Results from a longitudinal panel survey. *Health & Place*, *23*, 97–103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.healthplace.2013.05.006>
- White, M. P., Elliott, L. R., Grellier, J., Economou, T., Bell, S., Bratman, G. N., ... & Fleming, L. E. (2021). Associations between green/blue spaces and mental health across 18 countries. *Scientific Reports*, *11*(1), 8903. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-87675-0>
- White, M. P., Pahl, S., Wheeler, B. W., Depledge, M. H., & Fleming, L. E. (2017). Natural environments and subjective wellbeing: Different types of exposure are associated with different aspects of wellbeing. *Health & Place*, *45*, 77–84. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.healthplace.2017.03.008>
- Xu, L., Zeng, S., Jiang, Z., Sun, Z., Li, H., & Xu, L. (2023). From peaks to people: The association between physical topography and generalized trust in China. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, *91*, 102136. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2023.102136>

PSYCHOLOGY OF LANDSCAPES

- Zhang, D., Jin, X., Wang, L., & Jin, Y. (2023). Form and color visual perception in green exercise: Positive effects on attention, mood, and self-esteem. *Journal of Environmental Psychology, 88*, 102028. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2023.102028>
- Pasanen, T. P., Yli-Tuomi, T., Tiittanen, P., & Lanki, T. (2025). More green, less annoying? The moderating effects of greenery near home, noise sensitivity, and nature relatedness on road traffic noise annoyance. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening, 104*, 128625. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2024.128625>
- Götz, F. M., Ebert, T., & Rentfrow, P. J. (2018). Regional cultures and the psychological geography of Switzerland: Person–environment–fit in personality predicts subjective wellbeing. *Frontiers in Psychology, 9*, 517. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2018.00517>